

Impact of Rural-Urban Migration on Socio-Economic Condition/Status Case study of Selected Large & Medium Scale Industries

Khalid Anwar

Associate Professor, Department of Economics
J.V. Jain (P.G.) College, Saharanpur (U.P)

Received : 06/05/2022

1st BPR : 14/05/2022

2nd BPR : 28/05/2022

Accepted : 06/06/2022

Abstract

Large scale population mobility and the consequent redistribution of population have a number of economic, ecological, social, political and demographic implications. As Spengler and Myers observe, "Migration consists of a variety of movements that can be described in the aggregate as an evolutionary and development-fostering process operating in time and space to correct rural-urban, inter-urban, and inter-regional imbalances. It also may spread information, when migrants are more skilled than those living in the regions of destination, and it may break the cake of custom enveloping migrants and make the latter a dynamic force.

Key words: Rural-Urban Migration, Socio-Economic Condition.

Introduction

As the urban ward drift of the population is caused mostly by the poor living conditions in the village, the most effective way to arrest it is obviously the all-round development of the rural areas. For we must strike at the root of the problem rather than at the consequence. Especially in a democratic set-up, the migration caused by the rural push can be effectively checked only by providing gainful employment opportunities and better living conditions in the village.

Agriculture which is relatively less capital intensive has tremendous potential for labour absorption. Development of non-farma activities can also help improve the rural economic conditions significantly.

Objective

The Objective of this paper is to study the Impact on Socio-Economic Condition/status of the migrants.

Socio-Economic Consequences:

Migration may have important economic effects on both the place of origin and destination. Migration from a region Uncharacterized by labour surplus or disguised unemployment usually helps to increase the average and marginal productivity of labour in that region. There is, however, a view that migration disfavors the emigrating region and favours the immigrating region and that migration would widen the development disparity between the regions because of the drain of resourceful persons from the relatively underdeveloped region to more developed region. However exodus of the more enterprising or innovative members of a community cannot legitimately be considered a loss if institutional barriers or lack of alternatives in rural areas deny such migrants access to opportunities of employment and income As long as migration draws upon the surplus labour and the disguised unemployment. it would help the emigrating Iregion. But it will certainly have adverse effects on the labour-sending region if migration proceeds to the extent of draining away the human resources capable of being utilized for the development of the region. When migration draws away the unemployed, including the "disguised unemployment" it would enable the

remaining population of the region to improve their living conditions. The drain of surplus manpower does not adversely affect the productivity of the region, on the other hand, the removal of disguised unemployment increases the average productivity. This would enable the remaining population to increase the per capita consumption since the total number of mouths to be fed by the given cake is reduced as a result of emigration.

If the rapidly prospering urban areas suffer from labour shortage, they stand to gain by immigration of labour. Urban areas, where employment opportunities are significantly expanding, usually have the power to attract large number of the labour of different skills.

Thus, the urbanward shift of population can accelerate economic growth. However, it should be realised that the phenomenon of 'over-urbanisation' creates a lot of negative externalities leading to numerous multidimensional problems.

If the urbanward drift of the population is motivated by the urban opportunities, the number, composition and characteristics of the migrants will be regulated by these full factors and the concomitant demand-supply elasticities would tend to bring in an equilibrium without the stresses and strains, of the adjustment and adaptation process being too severe. On the other hand, if migration to the cities is the consequence of the push exercised by the rural problems, the volume and characteristics of migrants may not have any relevance to the urban situation and this will have far-reaching deleterious and muddling implications, apart from incessantly straining the already palpably pathetic and inadequate civic amenities. The labour exporting regions may gain economically by the money brought in by the emigrants. " The influx of rural migrants to cities and towns has resulted in a steady out flow of cash from the urban to rural areas. Most migrants are single males, who, after securing urban employment, generally send a portion of their income to their village homes to supplement the meagre incomes of their families. Remittances not only sustain rural families, they also promote a village a money economy in place of the traditional exchange or barter economy".

Socio-Economic Conditions/Status of Respondent Migrants of Large Scale Industries:

Table 1 gives an idea of the socio-economic profile of the respondent migrants in the large scale industries in Saharanpur district. Out of the 110 respondents in L.K. Textile Mill, 90 (i.e., 81.8%) migrants have purchased durables like Radio, T.V. cycles, furnitures, woolen products and other household items; 5 (i.e., 4.6%) migrants have savings in different banks; 5 (i.e., 4.6%) have made investments in different businesses like shops, lending of money to people and the rest 10 (i.e., 9%) have purchased assets like gold, land and houses etc. Similarly, out of 100 respondent migrants in Star Paper Mill, 70 (i.e., 70%) have purchased consumer durables, 8 (i.e., 8%) have savings, 7 (i.e., 7%) have invested a considerable part of their income in different business and 15 (i.e., 15%) have purchased assets. Out of 40 respondents in Indian Tobacco Co. Ltd, 29 (i.e., 72.5%) have purchased costly consumer durables and the rest 11 (i.e., 27.5%) have spent some part of their income on the purchase of assets. Out of 30 respondent migrants in Gangeshwar Ltd. 24 (i.e., 80%) have consumer durables. Only 1 (i.e., 3.33%) have some saving in banks and the rest 5 (i.e., 16.67%) have purchased assets. Similarly out of 10 respondent migrants in Kissan Sugar Mill . 6 (i.e., 60%) have purchased durables, only 10% each (i.e., 1 each) have savings and investment and the rest 2 (i.e., 20%) have made assets after migrating to Saharanpur district.

Table 01
Socio-Economic Profile of Respondent Migrants of Large Scale Industries

S.No.	Name of Industries	Purchase of Durables	Savings	Investment	Assets Creation	Total
1.	L.K. Textiles Mill	90 (81.8)	5 (4.8)	5 (4.8)	10 (9.0)	110
2.	Star Paper Mill	70 (70)	8 (8)	7 (7)	15 (15)	100
3.	Indian Tobacco Co.	29	-	-	11	40

	Ltd	(72.5)			(27.5)	
4.	Gangeshwar Ltd	24 (80)	1 (3.33)	-	5 (16.67)	30
5.	Kissan Sugar Mill	6 (60)	1 (10)	1 (10)	2 (20)	10

Source: Data collected through questionnaires.

NOTE: Bracketed figure are percentages to number of migrants.

Socio-Economic Conditions/Status of Respondent Migrants of Medium Scale Industries:

The socio-economic profile of the respondent migrants in medium scale industries of Saharanpur is given in Table 2

Out. of 4 respondent migrants in Saharanpur Engg. Works 3 (i.e., 75%) has purchased durables like T.V. Cycle. Radio, furnitures. Out of their monthly income after migration, and the rest 1 (i.e., 25%) has purchased some assets. Same was the case in case of Indana Spices and Food Co. Ltd. But all the 3 respondent migrants in Rakesh Chemicals have purchased durables like T.V. radio, cycle, furniture's etc. out of their monthly income after migration. Similarly the only 1 respondent migrant (i.e.,100%) in Hari Kishan Flour Mill has purchased some durables out of his monthly income. Out of 2 each respondent migrants in The cooperative Co. Ltd and U.P. cooperative Co. Ltd., 1 each (i.e., 50%) has purchased some durables and the rest 1 each (i.e., 50%) has purchased some assets Out of their income after migration. Out of 2 respondent migrants in Suraj Automobiles 1 (i.e., 50%) have purchased some consumer durables like T.V., radio, cycle, furnitures etc. and the rest 1 (i.e., 50%) has made savings in different banks. Out of their monthly income after migrating to Saharanpur district and getting a job in the medium scale industries.

Table 2
Socio-Economic Profile of Respondent Migrants of medium Scale Industries

S. No.	Name of Industries	Purchase of Durables	Savings	Investment	Assets Creation	Total
1.	Saharanpur Engg. Works	3 (75)	-	-	1 (25)	4
2.	Indian Spices & Food Co. Ltd.	3 (75)	-	-	1 (25)	4
3.	Hakesh Chemicals	3 (100)	-	-	-	3
4.	The Cooperative Co. Ltd	1 (50)	-	-	1 (50)	2
5.	Suraj Automobile	1 (50)	1 (50)	-	-	2
6.	U.P Cooperative Co. Ltd	1 (50)	-	-	1 (50)	2
7.	Hari Kishan Flour Mill	1 (100)	-	-	-	1

Source: Data collected through questionnaires.

NOTE: Bracketed figures are percentages to number of migrants.

Conclusion

It may be concluded from the above analysis that the socio-economic conditions of all the respondent migrant in both the types of industries of Saharanpur district have improved after migration. This was reflected in their savings and consumptions behavior.

The respondent migrants of large scale industries have not only purchased consumer durables out of their monthly incomes. But have also made savings in different banks, they have invested in different business as well as made assets.

The respondent migrants of large scale and medium scale industries prefer spending their income in purchasing consumer durables and assets rather than in saving and investment.

Urban migration and consequently the increase in income of the migrant laborers have improved their economic condition to a considerable extent. These industries, by raising income levels of the migrant laborers, have brought about significant changes in their standard of living and the social and cultural attitudes.

By the operation of the demonstration effect, the migrants have been switching over to a new way of life "urbanized rural life". Some of the migrants have acquired motor-cycles and scooters and visit their native place. In the evening, after coming from their factory/industry, they go to nearby markets for shopping and recreation. They also visit the film talkies occasionally.

It was also found out during the field survey that some of the migrants have constructed their own houses at the outskirts of the city for residential purposes. The migrants have also been sending their children to the schools for education.

References

1. Kingsley. D., "The origin and growth of Urbanisation in the World.", American Journal of Sociology. March 1955. P.429.
2. Connell. J., Migration from Rural Areas. The Evidence from Village Studies. LTD Oxford University Press. 1976. P.91-92)
3. Joseph. J. Spengler and George C. Myers. "Migration and Social-Economic Development : Today and Yesterday". In Alan A. Brown and Egon Neuberger. International Migration a comparative-Perspective (New York : Academic Press. 1977). P.11.
4. Noble. A.G. and Dutta. A.K. "Modernisation", In Noble A.G. and Dutta, A. K. Indian urbanization and Planning (New Delhi : Tata MaGraw Hill. 1977) P.216.
5. Bartel. A.P., J. Lab. Eco. Oct. 1989. 7(4) P. 371-91.

